

Open Neuroimaging Project

OHBM OSR Sponsor Address

WIN Open Tools

Investing in the community

- **Engage** in developing infrastructure
- **Empower** to create and share resources
- **Grow** from first contact to sustained participation and leadership

A screenshot of the Open Win Community website. The browser address bar shows "open.win.ox.ac.uk". The page has a dark header with "Home | Open WIN" and a search bar. The main content area is white with a light blue sidebar on the left. The sidebar contains a "Home" section with a dropdown arrow, listing "Guiding Principles", "Using this repository", "Contributing", "Acknowledgements", "License & Citation", and "Join us on Slack or by Email". Below this are sections for "Open MR Protocols", "Open Tasks", "Open Data", "Open Analysis", "Git and GitLab", "Open WIN Community", and "Open Access Publishing", each with a dropdown arrow. The main content area features a large heading "Open Research at the Wellcome Centre for Integrative Neuroimaging (WIN)" followed by a paragraph: "Find out how to share your research outputs effectively and responsibly, for improved impact, access and collaboration". Below this is a paragraph: "This repository is the hub for information on how to employ open research practices at the Wellcome Centre for Integrative Neuroimaging (WIN). The material shared here is written and maintained by an active community of WIN researchers, and is intended to support all WIN members in using the sharing infrastructure created by the WIN Open Neuroimaging Project." A bolded instruction follows: "Jump straight into one of the sections below, or use the sidebar to find out more about this repository." At the bottom of the main content area is a grid of six colored boxes with icons and text: "MR Protocols" (dark red, padlock icon), "Tasks" (dark brown, carrot icon), "Data" (light brown, pie chart icon), "Analysis" (teal, code icon), "Git and GitLab" (blue, Git icon), and "Community" (dark blue, group of people icon). At the bottom left of the page, it says "This site uses Just the Docs, a documentation theme for Jekyll."

A screenshot of a web browser displaying the Open Win Community website. The browser's address bar shows "open.win.ox.ac.uk". The page title is "What to include in your repository | Open WIN". The left sidebar contains a navigation menu with items like "Home", "Open MR Protocols", "Open Tasks", "Open Data", "Open Analysis", "Git and GitLab", "Tutorials", "What to include in your repository" (highlighted with a blue arrow), "How to license your code", "Making your repository citable", "Open WIN Community", and "Open Access Publishing". The main content area is titled "What to include in your repository" and lists several sections: "README.md" with a list of seven numbered items (The Problem, The Solution, What are we doing?, What do we need?, Who are we?, Contact us, Acknowledgements and citation); "CONTRIBUTING.md" with a paragraph of text; "CITATION.cff" with a paragraph of text and a link to "The Turing Way"; and "LICENSE.md" with a paragraph of text. At the bottom of the page, there is a footer note: "This site uses Just the Docs, a documentation theme for Jekyll."

<https://open.win.ox.ac.uk/protocols/>

SIEMENS
Healthineers

A screenshot of the WIN MR Database website. The browser address bar shows "open.win.ox.ac.uk". The page header includes "MR Protocols" and logos for "wellcome centre integrative neuroimaging" and "Search". A navigation breadcrumb shows "You are here: Home". The main heading is "WIN MR Database". Below it is a search bar with the placeholder text "Enter keywords to search protocols" and a blue "Search" button. A dropdown menu is open, showing "How to search" with a sub-heading "Welcome to the WIN MR Database". The text below the sub-heading reads: "Enter some keywords to help us find matching protocols. You can search by:". A bulleted list follows: "MRI modality (e.g. T1, T2, Bold, Diffusion, etc)", "Clinical application (e.g. stroke, dementia)", "Scanner model or coil type", "Project code or name e.g. biobank", "Citation reference (author, title, publication, year, DOI)", and "... plus any other keywords". The footer contains links for "Privacy Notice", "Cookies policy", "About", "WIN Centre", and "Open Neuroimaging Project".

<https://open.win.ox.ac.uk/protocols/>

SIEMENS
Healthineers

A screenshot of a web browser displaying a research article snippet. The browser's address bar shows "frontiersin.org". The page title is "Magnetic Resonance Imaging Data Acquisition and Analysis". The text describes the acquisition and analysis of fMRI and T1-weighted anatomical images. A blue highlight covers the sentence: "The full acquisition protocol, along with radiographic procedure is available from the Open WIN MR Protocols database here: 10.5281/zenodo.6107724." Below the text, there is a red document icon in a circle.

frontiersin.org

What to include in your repository | Open WIN | WIN MR Protocols 2018_114 Seven Day Prucalopri... | Frontiers | The Effect of the 5-HT4 Agonist, Pruca...

4 matches < > Q- protoc Done

LOGIN / REGISTER

Magnetic Resonance Imaging Data Acquisition and Analysis

Blood-oxygenation-level-dependent (BOLD) fMRI and T1-weighted anatomical images were acquired using a 3-Tesla Siemens Prisma scanner, equipped with a 32-channel head matrix coil (Siemens, Erlangen, Germany). Here we report results from the faces task. Participants also completed an encoding memory task and an arterial spin labelling (ASL) during the scan, the details of which have been published previously (20) with cerebral blood flow data also included here as a covariate. Results from the resting state scan will be reported elsewhere. Foam padding and a head restraint were used to control head movement. Further details of fMRI and structural Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) acquisition can be found in the **Supplementary Material**. The full acquisition protocol, along with radiographic procedure is available from the Open WIN MR Protocols database here: [10.5281/zenodo.6107724](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6107724).

Faces imaging data were analysed with FSL.² fMRI data were pre-processed : analysed using FEAT (FMRI Expert Analysis Tool), version 6.0.4, part of FSL (FMRIB's Software Library; see text footnote 2). For further information on the pre-

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A screenshot of a web browser displaying the Open MR Protocols website. The browser address bar shows "open.win.ox.ac.uk". The page header includes "MR Protocols" and "wellcome centre integrative neuroimaging". The main content area shows the protocol name "Protocol: 2018_114 Seven Day Prucalopride" and a "Download" button. Below this, there are sections for "Open Access Status" (with a checked checkbox for "Open Access" and a "Stable URL" link), "Version Info" (with "Original Creation Date", "Version", and "Version History" details), and "Reference List" (with "Protocol Citation" and "Weblink DOI" fields).

